

LARGE DISPLACEMENT EFFECTS IN THE DCB TEST FOR INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE IN MODES I AND II

by

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ABSTRACT

Analyses are given for both modes I and II in a DCB test. It is pointed out that exact values are given when the true moments at the beam roots are used in the calculation. For large displacements this can be achieved by directly measuring the moment arm of the applied load. If only the load point displacements and the curved crack lengths are known corrections can be made using large displacement beam theory. Correction factors for this purpose are given.

INTRODUCTION

Failure in composites from interlaminar crack propagation is a widely used design criterion. When significant delamination occurs there is a reduction in bending stiffness which can impair the performance of the structure. A defect in the interlaminar region can arise from poor resin distribution or from impact damage and such defects can be propagated by the loads applied to the structure. The resistance to their formation in the case of damage and to propagation generally is determined by the energy per unit area necessary and this can be described in terms of G_c when the structure behaves as a linear elastic system. Two modes of propagation can be visualised; the opening mode I which occurs in the usual DCB test shown in fig.1 (a) and the shear mode II, fig.1 (b) in which the crack is induced by shear stresses when the arms are bent in the same direction. It is reasonable to suppose that the toughness for these modes will be different; i.e. G_{Ic} and G_{IIc} so tests of each type are frequently performed to characterise laminates and in particular to compare the toughness of matrix resins in-situ. Special difficulties arise when tough resins are employed [1] since thick laminates are hard to make and the rather slender sections have to be subjected to large loads to effect crack propagation, particularly in mode II. This leads to large displacements in the specimen arms and non-linearity in the loading diagrams which cast doubt on the usual methods of analysis. This paper looks at this problem for both tests and suggests some simple procedures to avoid the difficulty.

G ANALYSIS

Let us first confine our attention to mode I and consider the section at the root of the arms as shown in fig. 2, G may be found by considering a contour at the crack tip, ABCD, and noting, that in this case, there are no tractions on AB, BC, or CD so G may be found from considering only the beam roots, AD. G may be defined as;

$$G = \frac{1}{B} \left(\frac{dU_e}{da} - \frac{dU_s}{da} \right) \quad (1)$$

where U_e is the external work performed during the crack growth da and U_s is the strain energy [2]. The rotation ϕ produced by the moments are given by;

$$\frac{d\phi}{dx} = \frac{M}{EI} \quad (2)$$

where x is the axial distance along the beam and I is the second moment of area, $BD^3/12$ in this case. If the crack grows a distance da , as shown in fig.2, then the root rotates by; $(M/EI).da$ so we have; $dU_e = 2M.d\phi$ and

$$\frac{dU_e}{da} = 2.M^2/EI \quad (\text{The factor 2 is to include both arms.})$$

The strain energy within the contour is initially zero but when a grows it increases by,

$$dU_s = 2. \left(\frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{M^2}{EI} \right) \cdot da$$

and on substituting in equation (1) we have;

$$G_I = \frac{M^2}{BEI} \quad (3)$$

G_I is used since the deformation is in mode I only here. The analysis used may be extended to cover any loading and gives a very powerful method for finding G in such systems [3]. Equation (3) is, however, a most important result since it shows that G is determined **entirely** by the **local** values of M,B,E and I at the beam roots. It does not matter how these vary within the arms; it is only the local values which determine G. This concept is, of course, entirely compatible with the local stress field concepts embodied in stress intensity factor solutions.

For the small displacement case we can calculate G_I very easily since $M=Pa$ so that

$$G_I = \frac{P^2 a^2}{BEI} \quad (4)$$

and noting that for tapered beams it is the local values of B and I which are needed. If the load point opening δ is measured then for parallel beams;

$$\delta/2 = \frac{Pa^2}{3EI} \quad (5)$$

and

$$G_I = 3/2 \frac{P\delta}{Ba} \quad (6)$$

and G_I may be found without knowing E for the specimen separately.

The energy method of calculation shown in fig.3 can be derived directly from equation (5) since the strain energy U_s is given by ;

$$U_s = \delta/2 \cdot P = \frac{P^2 a^3}{3EI} = 3/4 \frac{\delta^2 EI}{a^3}$$

and G may be defined as,

$$G = - \frac{1}{B} \frac{dU_s}{da} \Big|_{\delta \text{ const}} = 9/4 \frac{\delta^2 EI}{Ba^4} = \frac{P^2 a^2}{BEI} \text{ as before.}$$

$-dU_s$ may be taken directly from the loading diagram, as shown in fig.3; a method which is sometimes employed.

LARGE DISPLACEMENTS

When large displacements occur the specimen appears as in fig.4 and the crack length a , is now the curved length of the arm. The load-displacement diagrams is no longer straight but curved as shown in fig.5. This non-linearity is entirely due to geometry changes and the material, of course, remains linear. It should be noted now that equation (3) is still rigorously true so that if \bar{x} , the distance from the crack tip to the load line, is measured then

$$G_I = \frac{P^2 \bar{x}^2}{BEI} \quad (7)$$

Similarly the shaded area between the curved lines in fig.5 will give G exactly. Neither of these methods is particularly easy, especially that using energy, and it is frequently easier to measure a from marks on the specimen and δ from the overall displacement. Fortunately it is quite easy to analyse the finite displacements in beams [4] using the angles of rotation and in terms of that at the load point, α , as shown in fig.4, we have the results [4];

$$\delta/2a = \frac{I_2}{I_1}, \quad \frac{Pa^2}{3EI} = \frac{I_1^2}{6} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{x}^2 = \frac{2EI}{P} \cdot \sin \alpha$$

where

$$I_1 = \int_0^\alpha \frac{d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin \alpha - \sin \phi)}} \quad \text{and} \quad I_2 = \int_0^\alpha \frac{\sin \phi d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin \alpha - \sin \phi)}}$$

I_1 and I_2 can only be evaluated numerically but for small α , $I_1 = 2\alpha^{1/2}$ and $I_2 = 4/3 \alpha^{3/2}$ giving;

$$\delta/2a = 2/3 \alpha = \frac{Pa^2}{3EI} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{x} = a$$

the small displacement result. From equation (7) we may express G_I in terms of a correction factor to be applied to the small displacement result; i.e.

$$G_I / G_s = \frac{4 \sin \alpha}{I_1^2} = F_I, \quad \left(G_s = \frac{P^2 a^2}{BEI} \right) \quad (8)$$

F_I and I_2/I_1 are given as functions of α in Table 1 so that if $\delta/2a$ is measured then α and F_I can be found and an exact result derived.

The use of end blocks can effect the calibration but can be included in the analyses as shown in [4]. However provided they are made small with the loading point close to the specimen, the effect is not large.

MODE II TESTS

The mode II configuration shown in fig.1(b) requires a slightly different derivation of G since the two moments act in the same sense so there is a nett moment $2M$ on the section. Although there is now a moment at BC in fig.2 it does not move when a increases so the energy sums may again be performed at the beam root. The rotations are now over and above those already existing due to $2M$ i.e.

$$\frac{d\phi_0}{dx} = \frac{2M}{8EI} \quad \left(\text{The full section second moment of area is } \frac{B(2D)^3}{12} = 8I \right)$$

$$\text{and } \frac{dU_e}{da} = 2M \left(\frac{M}{EI} - \frac{M}{4EI} \right) = 3/2 \frac{M^2}{EI}$$

$$\text{with } \frac{dU_s}{da} = 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{M^2}{EI} \right) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(2M)^2}{8EI} = 3/4 \frac{M^2}{EI}$$

$$\text{so that } G_{II} = \frac{3}{4} \frac{M^2}{BEI}$$

The load is shared between the two arms here so $M = Pa/2$ giving;

$$G_{II} = \frac{3}{16} \frac{P^2 a^2}{BEI} \quad (9)$$

For large displacements the exact value of G_{II} is obtained by using \bar{x} instead of a as shown in fig.6, and again a correction may be computed if only the total displacement δ and a are measured. Here the result is somewhat more complex because of the two sections of the beam and the slope at the crack front, α_1 , is also involved. The required integrals are ;

$$\sqrt{\frac{Pa^2}{EI}} = \int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin\alpha - \sin\phi)}} = I_3$$

$$L/a - 1 = \frac{1}{I_3} \int_0^{\alpha_1} \frac{4\sin\phi \, d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin\alpha + 3\sin\alpha_1 - 4\sin\phi)}}$$

$$\text{and } \delta/a = \frac{1}{I_3} \left[\int_{\alpha_1}^{\alpha} \frac{\sin\phi \, d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin\alpha - \sin\phi)}} + \int_0^{\alpha_1} \frac{4 \sin\phi \, d\phi}{\sqrt{(\sin\alpha + 3 \sin\alpha_1 - 4 \sin\phi)}} \right] \quad (10)$$

[The factor of 4 in the second term was inadvertently omitted in the equivalent expression in [4].]

The correction factor for G_s given in equation (9) is;

$$G_{II} / G_s = \frac{4(\sin\alpha - \sin\alpha_1)}{I_3^2} = F_{II}, \quad G_s = 3/16 \frac{P^2 a^2}{BEI}$$

This is rather an awkward procedure since α_1 must be found but if it is assumed to be small, i.e. $\alpha_1 \ll \alpha$, which is reasonable for $a/L \rightarrow 1$ then the procedure can be simplified as;

$$\delta/a \cdot \psi = \frac{I_2}{I_1}, \quad \psi = \frac{2(1+a/L)}{(3+a/L)} \text{ and } F_{II} = \frac{F_I}{\psi^{-2}} \left[1 - \frac{2(1-\psi)}{F_I^{1/2}} \right] \quad (11)$$

When both $a/L \rightarrow 0$ and 1, $\delta/L \rightarrow I_2/I_1$ then the equations (10) give limits on F_{II} of F_I at $a/L = 1$ and of $\cos^2\alpha$ at $a/L = 0$. Fig.7 shows an exact computation of F_{II} for $\alpha = 1$ where δ/L changes with a/L but is convenient to perform. Also shown is equation (11) with the two bounds and it is clear that the approximation is good, even in this rather extreme case, for $F_{II} \geq \cos^2\alpha$. It is suggested that a useful procedure in a test would be to find α using $\delta/L = I_2/I_1$ in Table I from which the bounds F_I and $\cos^2\alpha$ can be found ($\cos^2\alpha$ is also shown in Table I). F_{II} is derived from equation (11) within the limits $\cos^2\alpha < F_{II} < F_I$. If equation (11) gives $F_{II} < \cos^2\alpha$ then $\cos^2\alpha$ should be used.

Similar corrections can be computed to include the effects of end blocks [4].

CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that exact values of G_I and G_{II} can be obtained if the true bending moment at the beam roots is found. This can be done by direct measurement in which case the simple analysis will suffice. If only load point displacement and crack growth are known, the simplest experiments, these may be corrected by the procedure given

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TABLE I

α (rad)	I_2/I_1	F_1	$\cos^2\alpha$
0.1	.066	.994	.990
0.2	.133	.977	.961
0.3	.198	.953	.913
0.4	.263	.914	.848
0.5	.326	.869	.770
0.6	.387	.815	.681
0.7	.446	.755	.585
0.8	.504	.688	.485
0.9	.558	.617	.386
1.0	.610	.542	.292
1.1	.660	.464	.206
1.2	.707	.385	.131
1.3	.752	.304	.072

FIG.1. DOUBLE CANTILEVER BEAM (DCB) TEST

FIG.2. CRACK ROOT CONTOUR

FIG.3. ENERGY METHOD

FIG.4. LARGE DISPLACEMENT

FIG.5. LOAD-DISPLACEMENT DIAGRAM

FIG.6. LARGE DISPLACEMENTS IN MODE I

FIG.7. EXACT VALUES OF F_{II} COMPARED WITH EQUATION (11) FOR $\alpha = 1$ RAD, CONSTANT